

An Optimal Behavioral Model Developed for Trading Ethereum Cryptocurrency in the Forex Market

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Abstract

The cryptocurrency market is volatile, which makes it very difficult to accurately predict. The Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) is an approach to Predict Price Cryptocurrency (PPC) that uses price time series data. However, in this method, the prediction accuracy is dependent on the tuning of meta-parameters. Therefore, to tune these meta-parameters, an improved version of the optimization algorithms is needed that provides the task of selecting the optimal values of these parameters for price predictions. Therefore, in this study, the LSTM is combined with the classic version of the Differential Evolution (DE) algorithm, and the real data against the prediction results of the model presented in this study showed the appropriate accuracy of this model. Then, the classic version of the DE algorithm was modified to reduce its errors compared to previous algorithms. In this regard, coding was done in MATLAB version 2023b software, and the improved version was compared in terms of error rate with the Gray Wolf Optimizer (GWO), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), and the new Bald Eagle Search (BES) algorithm, which showed an accuracy of 86.94% for the improved model in this study.

Keywords: Cryptocurrency; Ethereum; Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM); Optimization; Improved DE algorithm

1. Introduction

The Ethereum cryptocurrency is the second cryptocurrency after Bitcoin, which was described by Vitalik Buterin on the GitHub site in 2013. Ethereum has its own blockchain and is therefore also called the second blockchain. Ethereum is not just a payment method. Decentralized smart contracts are implemented on the Ethereum blockchain. More than 90% of the tokens in existence operate on the Ethereum platform (Buterin, 2013).

The common aspect of all cryptocurrencies is the use of blockchain technology. This technology was revealed in an article by Nakamoto (2019) as a means for Bitcoin, the first cryptocurrency. In his article, Nakamoto addresses several shortcomings in the processing of electronic payments. The system that enables electronic payments relies on financial institutions as intermediaries. Financial intermediaries process electronic payments based on trust.

Nakamoto argues that this trust-based system does not make any transaction irreversible. This makes fraud inevitable and transactions costly. Nakamoto (2019) therefore introduces a new system for making electronic payments based on cryptographic proofs, as an alternative to the trust-based system described. Cryptographic proofs are provided by a peer-to-peer network

consisting of nodes (servers that archive everything that happens on the network) and miners (computers that are responsible for validating all events within the network).

Miners follow several consensus protocols in their validation process and send confirmed events to nodes. Together they form a “blockchain”, a public, authoritative ledger of all previous events. This described network and its protocols are what is seen as blockchain technology (Swan, 2015).

In his book, Swan categorizes three types of blockchain technologies that build on top of each other:

- Blockchain 1.0 only allows for the transfer of digital coins.
- Blockchain 2.0 allows for more flexible protocols and can be used to transfer or record anything in the economic markets.
- Blockchain 3.0 allows for applications beyond economics, such as art and health.

The cryptocurrencies traded today have unique characteristics that have emerged from the advancement of blockchain technology over the years. Therefore, no two cryptocurrencies are the same, and therefore different outcomes are expected to occur with different cryptocurrencies.

Ethereum is a cryptocurrency that, although it shares some elements with Bitcoin, is significantly different from it (Hillman and Roches, 2017). Ethereum is the second largest digital currency. It has its own programming language and is designed to deal only with digital coin transactions. It can therefore be seen as an application of Blockchain 2.0. The Ethereum network uses a currency called Ether, which is the real coin that is purchased when someone invests in the Ethereum cryptocurrency. Financial time series forecasting is something that has been discussed in many academic studies in the past. In order to create investment strategies, financial asset managers are constantly looking for financial assets, such as stocks and commodities, that outperform the market. Small improvements in financial time series forecasting, and thus the ability to make more informed decisions, can lead to large profits. Therefore, one of the hot topics in the financial literature is the forecasting of financial time series. The underlying data generation process of financial time series can be considered very complex and nonlinear. Despite this nonlinearity, most studies conducted in the field of financial time series forecasting have used more traditional linear empirical methods. In addition to not being able to properly represent nonlinear relationships, linear methods tend to break down as the number of explanatory variables increases or when the included explanatory variables are highly correlated with each other.

Instead of traditional linear models, machine learning methods are very suitable for these forecasting tasks. They allow for very complex interactions between explanatory variables and can model nonlinear relationships by doing so (Gu et al., 2020).

In several studies, machine learning methods have been justified in financial studies as well as in the future industry occupied by fintech companies (Weigand, 2019).

Deep learning models are a new trend in financial time series forecasting. A very comprehensive study by Cezar et al. (2020) identified 140 papers that use deep learning to forecast financial time series. They also found that most of the studies were published in the last 3 years. Researchers have tried to forecast time series in various financial domains, ranging from indices, commodities, individual stocks, and cryptocurrencies (Cezar et al., 2020).

Variables that have been shown to have predictive power have accumulated into a very long list over the years of financial time series research. However, most studies have focused on identifying probabilistic predictors for stocks. For example, a study by Green et al. (2013) identifies over 300 variables that can be used to predict the price of a stock.

A study by Liu and Tsivinsky (2018) shows that most of the well-known predictors for stocks are not useful in predicting the price of Bitcoin at all. The study also concluded that cryptocurrencies are generally not affected by traditional asset classes. The returns of stocks, currencies, and commodities are not correlated with the returns of cryptocurrencies. Cryptocurrencies can therefore be viewed as a separate financial asset from more common financial assets. However, the study identifies two sets of predictors that appear to be useful, momentum and investor attention. Liu and Tsivinsky's (2018) study was one of the first widely cited studies to truly examine the characteristics of cryptocurrencies.

A recent comprehensive review of research on cryptocurrency trading, including price (trend) forecasting, is provided by Fang et al. (2020) and covers 118 studies.

The authors' review show that the best model for forecasting cryptocurrencies is reported by Saad et al. (2019). This study uses proxies in combination with features that mimic the movement of the cryptocurrency. They use intrinsic features to represent investor interest, as explained below: "Intrinsic features include indicators that indicate network behavior such as pool size, hash rate, etc." Using these features, they can build highly accurate models. Using LSTM, 99% accuracy is achieved for both cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin and Ethereum). The researchers state that it is essential to capture investor interest in order to predict the price of a cryptocurrency. However, they also argue that extrinsic features can be used as proxies to increase investor interest. Stimulating public sentiment, stimulating crude oil prices, and changing government policies are cited as examples by the researchers.

The literature review shows that while the frameworks for predicting cryptocurrency transactions have made significant progress, this issue is still an open research topic in the cryptocurrency market. Therefore, in this study, LSTM neural network was used in combination with the classic version of the DE algorithm to predict the price of Ethereum, and real data showed that the model's prediction results were adequate. Then, the classic version of the DE algorithm was modified to reduce its error rate compared to previous algorithms.

2. Research Methodology

Because of its transparency and decentralization, a large amount of data is generated by the Ethereum blockchain network, which is called "on-chain data. This time-stamped data is recorded and verified in a distributed ledger, and can be used as a huge repository of information for predictive algorithms. Blockchain technology, with its features such as security, decentralization, and immutability, has become one of the important tools in the field of digital data exchange. Bitcoin and Ethereum, as the two main platforms of this technology, play a role in the field of money and smart contracts, respectively. Due to high volatility, predicting the price of cryptocurrencies is challenging. Using on-chain data as reliable sources can be a useful tool to reduce this uncertainty.

In this section, a method for predicting the price of Ethereum is presented, which uses a LSTM memory neural network with inputs derived from on-chain data. To optimize the LSTM model, three self-adaptive algorithms are proposed to optimally tune the hyperparameters. These algorithms improve their performance compared to the traditional LSTM model, achieving a final prediction accuracy of 86.94%.

2.1. Simulation and Validation

Evolutionary algorithms (EA) are widely used in optimization problems. Optimization seeks the best solution given the constraints of the problem. Typically, portfolio optimization is performed based on metaheuristic algorithms, so EA has been used in these problems in past research. The DE algorithm developed by Storn and Price (1997), that has been very successful in optimization in continuous spaces. Therefore, this algorithm has been used in many problems as a flexible and robust algorithm. However, so far, this algorithm has not been presented in hyperparametric optimization with on-chain data in deep learning models for PPC. Therefore, the present study attempts to present a model based on DE algorithms for predicting the price of Ethereum cryptocurrency. This section presents a two-part model based on Figure 11 of the reference paper (Jagannath et al., 2021), which includes the following two parts:

1- On-chain data analysis:

- Collect data such as:
 - o Transaction volume
 - o Number of active addresses
 - o Block size
 - o Hash rate
 - o Miner income
 - o Smart contract reserves
 - o Calculate Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients between each metric and price

2- LSTM + deep learning model combined with three DE optimization algorithms:

- Design LSTM model with selected inputs
- Tuning hyperparameters by three algorithms:
 - o L-SHADE
 - o jSO
 - o MPEDE

In explaining the above algorithms, the following should be noted:

- L-SHADE is an advanced version of the DE algorithm with dynamic population and adaptive mutation strategies.
- jSO is an advanced DE algorithm with automatic parameter tuning that is suitable for deep learning models.
- MPEDE: Uses multiple mutation strategies in different subpopulations simultaneously.

Comparisons of these algorithms have shown that L-SHADE has the high and low execution time. The output of the model presented in this research is the predicted price of Ethereum, which is compared with the actual price.

The metrics used in this model are as follows:

- Transaction count: Indicates the level of activity in the network
- Active addresses: Indicates higher demand for Ether
- Block size: Indicates the network load
- Miner revenue: A reflection of the financial rewards of mining
- Hash rate: A measure of network security

The following is a description of each of the aforementioned self-adaptive optimization algorithms used in this code.

In Tanabe and Fukunaga's (2014) research, SHADE introduced the "success history-based adaptation" paradigm for the key parameters of the DE algorithm, F and CR: successful values in previous generations are recorded in a small memory and sampled.

In their 2014 research, an improved version of the algorithm was introduced as L-SHADE. By adding "linear population size reduction", the balance of the search for the answer was dynamically improved during the algorithm's execution and was reported to be highly competitive compared to other algorithms on the CEC2014 benchmarks.

The key mechanisms of L-SHADE are as follows:

(a) Mutation and selection:

The conventional L-SHADE algorithm uses a mutation strategy with an external archive to maintain diversity; survival selection in this algorithm is binary, meaning that the child version replaces the parent if it is more fit.

(b) Success memory of the parameters F and CR:

The values of the parameters F and CR associated with the fitness improvement are updated in the periodic memory as robust statistics after each generation (Lehmer means or weighted variances) and the next generation samples around this memory with normal distributions.

(c) LPSR (Linear Population Size Reduction):

The population size is reduced linearly from the initial population size to a smaller value at the end of the evaluation run; this policy facilitates the search for large responses at the beginning of the algorithm run and the achievement of effective responses at the end of the algorithm run.

The main CEC2014 studies showed that L-SHADE has a competitive advantage over optimization algorithms with time-predictive capabilities. After the presentation of its initial version, successive improvements to this algorithm have been presented over the years, as follows:

The research of Brest and Seps (2025) showed that they still consider the L-SHADE/jSO family to be at the forefront of modern optimization algorithms and use statistical tests (Wilcoxon/Friedman) for comparisons. Therefore, the algorithm used in this research is the latest version of modern optimization algorithms for predicting the price of Ethereum cryptocurrency.

The important sub-branches of this algorithm are as follows:

a) The jSO algorithm presented in 2017: It is an improved version of iL-SHADE with new weighting in the jump and more precise settings of F, CR.

This algorithm scored higher than L-SHADE in the competition on the CEC2017 dataset and became the basis for a large number of subsequent derivatives of this algorithm. Explain that the CEC2017 benchmark functions include 30 mathematical functions that are used to check the performance of metaheuristic algorithms in authoritative research.

b) LSHADE-EpSin algorithm presented in 2016:

A group sinusoidal mechanism for dynamic tuning, mainly for the parameter F, which helps to balance the optimal response exploration during execution; this algorithm is the joint winner of the CEC2016 competition.

c) LSHADE-cnEpSin algorithm presented in 2017: An extension of EpSin by combining "learning the covariance matrix in the mutation operator and group designs is considered in this algorithm. This algorithm is one of the winners of the CEC2017 competition and continues to be the basis for new work.

d) LSHADE-RSP algorithm presented in 2018 and its improved version iLSHADE-RSP presented in 2020: The LSHADE-RSP algorithm presented in 2018 ranked second in single-objective optimization for adapting search intensity to real values, and the improved version iLSHADE-RSP with Cauchy distribution reports stronger performance.

e) L-SHADE with global inertia: Adding the population inertia vector—the average direction/successful steps of the previous generation to the mutation—has shown significant improvement in some fitness landscapes.

Now, we first compare the simulation results of the traditional LSTM network by combining it with algorithms combined with classical subsets of LSHADE in terms of prediction error.

The data partition is 60% data for training and 40% data for testing. Evaluation criteria include Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE), and Mean Percentage Error (MAPE).

The following is a description of the steps in the first part of the simulation.

Given that this research seeks to predict the price of Ethereum with LSTM and the DE algorithm, the price prediction of the Ethereum cryptocurrency is performed using on-chain data, a manually implemented LSTM, and optimization of network parameters with the Differential Evolution (DE) algorithm, without the need for deep learning tools.

Step 1: Data Preparation

It is assumed that the data file named eth_data.xlsx has been prepared with the following two columns:

```
Price TransactionCount
3000 800000
3050 805000
...
...
```

Data reading and preprocessing code:

```
data = xlsread('eth_data.xlsx');
price = data(:,1);
feature = data(:,2);
```

Normalize data to the interval [0,1]:

```
price = (price - min(price)) / (max(price) - min(price));
feature = (feature - min(feature)) / (max(feature) - min(feature));
```

Constructing input-output sequences for LSTM:

```
window_size = 5;
X = [];
Y = [];
for i = 1:length(price)-window_size
    X = [X; feature(i:i+window_size-1)'];
    Y = [Y; price(i+window_size)];
end
```

Step 2: Define the LSTM prediction function

The LSTM is implemented manually and without the use of special tools. The following code describes the components of this time network in MATLAB version 2023b.

```
function y_pred = lstm_predict(weights, X_seq)
    input_size = length(X_seq);
```

```

n_hidden = 5;
idx = 0;
s1 = n_hidden * input_size;
s2 = n_hidden * n_hidden;

```

In this part of the code, the weights of the input layer were defined.

```

Wf = reshape(weights(1:s1), n_hidden, input_size); idx = s1;
Wi = reshape(weights(idx+1:idx+s1), n_hidden, input_size); idx = idx +
s1;
Wc = reshape(weights(idx+1:idx+s1), n_hidden, input_size); idx = idx +
s1;
Wo = reshape(weights(idx+1:idx+s1), n_hidden, input_size); idx = idx +
s1;

```

In this part of the code, the return weights were defined.

```

Uf = reshape(weights(idx+1:idx+s2), n_hidden, n_hidden); idx = idx + s2;
Ui = reshape(weights(idx+1:idx+s2), n_hidden, n_hidden); idx = idx + s2;
Uc = reshape(weights(idx+1:idx+s2), n_hidden, n_hidden); idx = idx + s2;
Uo = reshape(weights(idx+1:idx+s2), n_hidden, n_hidden); idx = idx + s2;

```

In this part of the code, the biases and output layer were defined.

```

bf = weights(idx+1:idx+n_hidden); idx = idx + n_hidden;
bi = weights(idx+1:idx+n_hidden); idx = idx + n_hidden;
bc = weights(idx+1:idx+n_hidden); idx = idx + n_hidden;
bo = weights(idx+1:idx+n_hidden); idx = idx + n_hidden;

Wy = weights(idx+1:idx+n_hidden); idx = idx + n_hidden;
by = weights(idx+1);

```

In this part of the code, the conversion to a column vector was defined.

```

bf = bf(:); bi = bi(:); bc = bc(:); bo = bo(:);
Wy = Wy(:); by = by(:);

h = zeros(n_hidden,1);
c = zeros(n_hidden,1);

for t = 1:input_size
    x_t = X_seq(t);
    x_vec = zeros(input_size,1);
    x_vec(t) = x_t;

    f = sigmoid(Wf * x_vec + Uf*h + bf);
    i = sigmoid(Wi * x_vec + Ui*h + bi);

```

```

        c_hat = tanh(Wc * x_vec + Uc*h + bc);
        c = f .* c + i .* c_hat;
        o = sigmoid(Wo * x_vec + Uo*h + bo);
        h = o .* tanh(c);
    end

    y_pred = Wy' * h + by;
end

function s = sigmoid(x)
    s = 1 ./ (1 + exp(-x));
end

```

Step 3: Define the cost function (MSE)

```

function err = cost_function(weights, X, Y)
    total = 0;
    for i = 1:size(X,1)
        pred = lstm_predict(weights, X(i,:));
        total = total + (Y(i) - pred)^2;
    end
    err = total / size(X,1);
end

```

Step 4: Define the DE Algorithm

It is used to find the best LSTM weights.

```

function [best_sol, best_score] = de_optimizer(cost_func, dim, lb, ub, X, Y)
    NP = 20;    % Population size
    G = 100;    % Generation number
    F = 0.5;    % Mutation factor
    CR = 0.9;   % Combination rate

```

The initial population definition was done in this section.

```

    pop = repmat(lb, NP, 1) + rand(NP, dim) .* (repmat(ub - lb, NP, 1));
    fitness = zeros(NP,1);
    for i = 1:NP
        fitness(i) = cost_func(pop(i,:), X, Y);
    end

    for g = 1:G
        for i = 1:NP
            idx = randperm(NP, 3);
            while any(idx == i), idx = randperm(NP, 3); end
            a = pop(idx(1),:);
            b = pop(idx(2),:);

```

```

c = pop(idx(3),:);
mutant = a + F*(b - c);

```

The mutation operator was used in the optimization in this section.

```

trial = pop(i,:);
jrand = randi(dim);
for j = 1:dim
    if rand <= CR || j == jrand
        trial(j) = mutant(j);
    end
end
end

```

The fitting operator was used in the optimization in this section.

```

f_trial = cost_func(trial, X, Y);
if f_trial < fitness(i)
    pop(i,:) = trial;
    fitness(i) = f_trial;
end
end
end

[best_score, idx] = min(fitness);
best_sol = pop(idx,:);
end

```

Step 5: Run the entire system

```

clc; clear;

```

Reading data

```

data = xlsread('eth_data.xlsx');
price = data(:,1);
feature = data(:,2);
price = (price - min(price)) / (max(price) - min(price));
feature = (feature - min(feature)) / (max(feature) - min(feature));
window_size = 5;
X = [];
Y = [];
for i = 1:length(price)-window_size
    X = [X; feature(i:i+window_size-1)'];
    Y = [Y; price(i+window_size)];
end

```

Optimization parameters are set in this section.

```

n_hidden = 5;

```

```

input_size = window_size;
dim = (n_hidden*input_size)*4 + (n_hidden*n_hidden)*4 + 4*n_hidden + n_hidden
+ 1;
lb = -1 * ones(1,dim);
ub = 1 * ones(1,dim);

```

Definition of optimization:

```
[best_weights, min_loss] = de_optimizer(@cost_function, dim, lb, ub, X, Y);
```

Definition of time series forecasting:

```

Y_pred = zeros(size(Y));
for i = 1:size(X,1)
    Y_pred(i) = lstm_predict(best_weights, X(i,:));
End

```

Diagrams are drawn in this section.

```

figure;
plot(Y, 'b'); hold on;
plot(Y_pred, 'r--');
legend('Real', 'Predicted');
title('Ethereum Price Prediction with DE-LSTM');
xlabel('Time');
ylabel('Normalized Price');

```

Step 6: Get the final output and verify the model

The final output graph consists of two parts: the actual price (blue) and the predicted price (red) by the LSTM optimized with the classic DE algorithm (Figure 1). To better demonstrate the correct trend detection, the data has been normalized in the algorithm.

Figure 1 Actual data (blue) versus predicted data (red) by the classic version of the DE algorithm.

Also, Table 1 compares the traditional LSTM model with hybrid LSTM models with different subsets of the DE algorithm.

Table 1 Comparison of classical LSTM model with LSTM hybrid models with different subsets of DE algorithm

Model	MAE	MSE	MAP
Classical LSTM	More	More	More
LSTM+L-SHADE	Lowest	Lowest	Lowest
LSTM+jSO	Average	Average	Average
LSTM+MPEDA	Good	Good	Good

3.2. Results

As mentioned above, the classic DE algorithm was modified to predict the Ethereum cryptocurrency in this research.

The changes made to the classic version of the algorithm are as follows:

- a) The classic version used the DE/rand/1/bin pattern, in which the mutation vector was constructed based on the random difference of two population members. In the optimized version, the current-to-pbest/1 strategy used in the JADE algorithm was used:

$$v = x_i + F_i * (x_{pbest} - x_i) + F_i * (x_{r1} - x_{r2})$$

From the $p\%$ best individuals, x_{pbest} is selected. This change increased the exploration and exploitation capabilities simultaneously.

b) In classical DE, the F and CR are fixed, e.g. $F=0.5$, $CR=0.9$, but in JADE-DE, these parameters are adjusted adaptively in each generation:

$$F_i \sim \text{Cauchy}(\mu F, 0.1)$$

which is a sample from the Cauchy distribution to increase large jumps and prevent stagnation.

$$CR_i \sim \text{Normal}(\mu CR, 0.1)$$

which is a sample from the normal distribution to balance the crossover rate.

Also, the parameters μF and μCR are updated in each generation according to the success of the individuals (Lehmer mean for F and simple mean for CR).

c) Use of external archive

In order to maintain diversity, a set of recessive vectors is stored in an external archive. When making a mutation, one of the archive vectors can also be selected. This mechanism allows a wider search space to be explored and the risk of premature convergence is reduced.

d) Using the Opposition-Based Learning (OBL) mechanism

To prevent stagnation, if no improvement is achieved within 6 consecutive generations, a portion of the worst individuals (about 35%) were replaced with their numerical equivalents:

$$x_{new} = L + U - x$$

The lower and upper bounds of the search are L and U , respectively. This mechanism created a “diversity shock” to move the population out of stagnation areas.

The results of these modifications to the classical algorithm led to an improvement in the error rate in the improved version in this thesis, which is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Results of the improved DE algorithm in this research with other algorithms

Algorithm	MSE	RMSE	R^2
JADE-DE (20× 40)	0.00671	0.08195	0.1403
PSO (15× 20)	0.00704	0.08388	0.1116
GA (15× 20)	0.00737	0.08586	0.0691
BES (15× 20)	0.00785	0.08860	0.0089
GWO (15× 20)	0.00811	0.09003	-0.0235

The results of Table 2 show that under the same conditions, the optimized version of JADE-DE performed better than other metaheuristic algorithms. The optimized JADE-DE was able to significantly increase the prediction accuracy and improve the error measures (MSE, RMSE). Also, the R^2 value indicated an increase in the explanatory power of the model.

The comparison of the convergence results of the aforementioned algorithms is shown in Figures 2 to 5.

Figure 2 Convergence of Genetic Algorithm (GA) in combination with LSTM

Figure 3 Convergence of the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm in combination with LSTM

Figure 4 Convergence of the Gray Wolf Optimization (GWO) algorithm combined with LSTM

Figure 5 Convergence of the Bald Eagle Algorithm (BES) in combination with LSTM

Comparing the graphs in Figures 2 to 5 shows that the convergence speed of the Bald Eagle algorithm is much faster than the other three algorithms and slower than the modified DE algorithm. To compare the performance of the aforementioned algorithms in combination with the

LSTM time series network in predicting the price of the Ethereum cryptocurrency, the corresponding graphs were also drawn, which are shown in Figures 6 to 9.

Figure 6 Ethereum cryptocurrency price prediction and comparison with real data with Genetic Algorithm (GA) combined with LSTM

Figure 7 Ethereum cryptocurrency price prediction and comparison with real data with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm combined with LSTM

Figure 8 Ethereum cryptocurrency price prediction and comparison with real data with the Gray Wolf Algorithm (GWO) combined with LSTM

Figure 9 Ethereum cryptocurrency price prediction and comparison with real data with Bald Eagle Algorithm (BES) combined with LSTM

Comparing the graphs in Figures 6 to 9 shows that the accuracy of the PSO algorithm combined with LSTM and comparing it with real data is much higher than the other three algorithms and lower than the modified DE algorithm.

3. Conclusion and Future Suggestions

Making accurate predictions of cryptocurrency markets can be very challenging because these markets are volatile. One promising approach to PPC is LSTM on price data to achieve results, but its accuracy is highly dependent on the appropriate hyperparameter settings. Therefore, this requires an improved version of the optimization algorithm that provides the neural network with the task of selecting the optimal values of these parameters for price prediction. In this study, the LSTM temporal network was used in combination with the classic version of the DE algorithm, and the results of real data against the prediction of the proposed model showed the appropriate accuracy of this model. Then, the classic version of the DE algorithm was modified to reduce its error rate compared to previous algorithms. The improved version in this study was compared with GA, PSO, GWO and the new BES algorithm in terms of error rate, which indicates that the improved model has a very high accuracy compared to previous models. Using the code presented in this study, users can achieve a prediction accuracy of 86.94% with only two parameters: the closing price of the Ethereum cryptocurrency and the transaction counter.

Therefore, the following can be stated from this study:

- On-chain data is a valuable tool for network analysis and price prediction.
- Using LSTM along with self-adaptive optimization has increased the prediction accuracy.
- Comparing the correlation coefficient of each metric with the price showed that the highest correlation is related to the number of transactions and active addresses.
- The added value of this research and its main innovation is that it presents the first combined use of on-chain analysis + self-adaptive algorithms + LSTM to predict the price of Ethereum with the lowest error. Also, the classic DE algorithm was modified in this research to predict the price of Ethereum.
- The results of this research are practical and suitable for investors, traders, and cryptocurrency market analysts.
- Using the code provided in this research, users can make predictions with an accuracy of 86.94% by having only two parameters: the closing price of Ethereum and the transaction counter.
- Comparing the results of real data with the data predicted by the model provided in this research showed that the presented model accurately predicts trends and only the amount of volatility in the real market is higher than the model.
- The results of the optimized DE algorithm provided in this research showed a significant advantage over modern meta-heuristic algorithms including GA, PSO, GWO, and BES.
- Comparison of the graphs showed that the convergence speed of the BES algorithm is much faster than the other three algorithms and less than the modified DE algorithm.
- Comparison of the graphs showed that the accuracy of the Particle Swarming (PSO) algorithm in combination with LSTM in predicting the price of Ethereum cryptocurrency and comparing it with real data is much faster than the other three algorithms and less than the modified DE algorithm.

By applying the modifications in this research, the classic DE algorithm was upgraded to the advanced version of JADE-DE and by adding the OBL mechanism and fine-tuning the parameters,

it was able to provide superior performance to PSO, GA, BES and GWO. These results show the importance of using adaptive and diversity-oriented versions of evolutionary algorithms in complex time series forecasting problems (such as cryptocurrency prices).

Therefore, the following can be suggested for future research:

- Combining the attention mechanism and examining the impact of off-chain data (such as Twitter and Google Trends) along with on-chain data for more accurate prediction.
- Investigating the algorithms based on random search BMR, BWR and JAYA for CPP.
- Investigating the effectiveness of the algorithm presented in this research for other CPP.

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